

CoARA Action Plan – TU/e

Introduction

The TU/e core values are the guiding principles for the TU/e Action plan. As TU/e community, we embrace and live our four [CORe values](#): Curious, Open, Respectful and Responsible.

Curious: We cherish curiosity, driving us to explore, question, and innovate, encouraging continuous learning and discovery.

Open: We value an open accessible culture and are transparent and trustworthy about our actions.

Respectful: We care for each other, treat everyone with respect, and welcome people from diverse backgrounds.

Responsible: We shape the future, led by example, and make a positive impact on society and sustainable innovation.

How are the university values translated into the TU/e Action Plan?

Built on the values, TU/e's Strategy 2030 states that the university is a human-centered employer, providing opportunities for talent for personal development and engaging the challenges of tomorrow together.

In late 2019, the Dutch public knowledge institutes and research funders published [the position paper](#) 'Room for everyone's talent: towards a new balance in the recognition and rewards of academics', arguing that the system of recognizing and rewarding academics needs modernization. For many years, research performance has determined the career path of academics, but this dominance is increasingly starting to crack. After all, education and impact are also determinants of the success of a modern knowledge institute. New developments related to Open Access and Open Science also place different demands on today's academics. In addition, the tackling of complex academic and societal issues requires greater collaboration between academics, which in turn requires different skills. TU/e is an active member of the national Recognition & Rewards (R&R) community.

In the period 2020-2022 a task force consisting of junior, mid-career, and senior scientific staff and HR worked on a TU/e vision that is the starting point for the new academic staff personnel policy.

Six leading principles for recognizing and rewarding excellence have been formulated:

Principle 1. Trust, support and appreciation

TU/e supports and enables faculty to develop their personal ambitions and objectives within the core domains and in compliance with the strategic objectives of the university. TU/e appreciates diversity in these ambitions and values the professional contributions made to the community. This

requires a culture of trust, dedicated coaching and mentoring, and a forward-looking approach while setting realistic objectives. These ambitions may change at different stages of a career.

Principle 2. Core competences

Faculty is active in both education and research. During the tenure track at the level of UD2, priority is given to research and education. Starting at the level of UD1, faculty may choose an emphasis on specific domains. This emphasis needs to be agreed upon with the team/group/department.

Principle 3. Balance between individual and the collective, and academic citizenship

Staff will be recognized for their contribution to their team(s) and their collegiality. Next to team spirit, academic citizenship is crucial to create a thriving academic community. A team is a powerful entity to achieve excellence. The composition of a team allows individuals to develop their talents (career diversification), while collectively meeting the objectives of the department and university.

Principle 4. Open Science

Engagement with Open Science will be stimulated and recognized and integrated in academic assessments.

Principle 5. High-quality academic leadership

High-quality leadership is dedicated to creating an inclusive, safe and trusting working environment in which individuals can thrive and collectively meet shared objectives. Our leaders embody our CORE values.

Principle 6. Fair and Individual Assessment based on an agreed upon profile

Assessment is based on an agreed upon profile and objectives, and a combination of narratives of past achievements and future visions, supported by demonstratable products and quantitative data tailored to the profile and discipline of the individual.

These six principles are the linking pin to the CoARA agreement and its commitments.

Goals and Actions

In 2023, [the roadmap](#) 'Room for everyone's talent in practice' was published. It outlines what the national R&R community aims to achieve on the five R&R priorities in the years ahead:

1. Diversification and vitalization of career paths
2. Achieving balance between individuals and the collective
3. Focusing on quality
4. Stimulating all aspects of Open Science
5. Encouraging academic leadership

For TU/e, this leads to the actions as mentioned in the table below:

Actions		
Recognition & Rewards program: overall coordination	TU/e Culture Barometer, May 2024	Result: full report The Culture Barometer is a national survey to gain insight into the recognition of R&R ambitions and culture change by academics. It reveals TU/e's positive encouragement to diversify career paths and a focus on quality over quantity. The Culture Barometer will be repeated in 2026.
Diversification and vitalization of career paths	Academic career paths policy Development matrix Everyone Professor, November 2024 Teacher Career paths, November 2024	In 2024 and 2025 TU/e will further develop the Academic Career paths policy to diversify career paths and provide transparent quality indicators in the Development Matrix. The career policy Everyone Professor aims to further equality and recognition of academic staff by granting assistant and associate professors the right to wear a toga, use the title 'professor' and grant the ius promovendi when they meet qualitative conditions. TU/e has developed teacher career paths to provide a framework for appointment and career opportunities for teachers.
Achieving balance between individuals and the collective	Stimulate teamwork and create high-performing teams Strategic workforce planning	In 2026 TU/e will develop Strategic Workforce Planning for its departments.
Focusing on quality	Biographical sketch CV, March 2024 Performance and development cycle Teacher professionalization	The Biographical Sketch is a template for an evidence-based CV for candidates preparing for assessments to substantiate their case. TU/e is redesigning its procedures for annual dialogue with the aim to become more development and future-oriented. The assessment procedures will be redesigned to increase transparency for all parties involved, and to increase the quality of academic assessment for promotions. Teacher professionalization starts with a University Teaching Qualification. However, TU/e will start continuous professional development for teachers in 2025.
Stimulating all aspects of Open Science	Open Science Agenda	TU/e will develop a database of best practices for Open Science activities and an intervention for assessment committees in 2025.
Encouraging academic leadership	Academic leadership development R&R toolbox/knowledge platform (e.g., open science training, inclusive assessment and selection, podcasts, journal articles, etc.) Exchange of best practices	TU/e has given leadership a more prominent place in academic assessment.

Timeframe The TU/e action plan is valid until 2027.

Action Plan 2024 – 2027 - TU/e analysis of 10 CoARA commitments

	Commitment in the Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment	State of play at TU/e in December 2023	Objectives and actions 2024-2027
1	Recognize the diversity of contributions to, and careers in, research in accordance with the needs and nature of the research	<p>In TU/e, Recognition & Rewards has mainly focused on developing more diverse academic career paths.</p> <p>The Policy for Teacher Career Paths was developed to be implemented in 2024.</p>	<p>Academic career paths allow assistant professors (UD2) to focus on education and research. The assessment for promotion will be based on these two domains.</p> <p>Academic careers will become more dynamic. Academics can build a career with a focus on education, research, and impact, leading to more diversity in academic profiles.</p> <p>The position of teachers is valued and strengthened. Their possibilities for development and growth are supported and broadened.</p> <p>Leadership will be a prerequisite for promotion in all career phases.</p>
2	Base research assessment primarily on qualitative evaluation for which peer review is central, supported by responsible use of quantitative indicators	<p>At the institutional and department level, TU/e uses the Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP). It provides a structured approach to assess the quality, relevance, and viability of research at Dutch universities and institutes every six years. An assessment committee of academic peers independent experts assesses the performance of the unit based on the self-evaluation and a site visit.</p> <p>TU/e has conducted a pilot in 2 research departments with an evidence-based narrative CV with the aim to focus on qualitative evaluation.</p>	<p>Academic assessment will be redesigned to create a uniform way of working. A uniform process is a prerequisite to improve quality and create transparency. All departments agree to ground rules for a compliant framework to ensure clarity and uniformity and make their way of working available in the university. Core members and fixed chairs are appointed to increase the quality of academic assessments.</p> <p>For each domain and each function level of assistant, associate, and full professors, there will be a set of main quality features / a description of the expected output or behavior.</p>

			The Biographical Sketch was introduced in all departments in March 2024 as an evidence-based narrative CV. Candidates will use the Biographical Sketch to substantiate their case for promotion.
3	Abandon inappropriate uses in research assessment of journal- and publication based metrics, in particular, inappropriate uses of Journal Impact Factor (JIF) and h-index	<p>TU/e has developed an Open Science White Paper to set the TU/e Open Science Agenda. Based on the (inter)national agenda, Open Science themes of relevance for TU/e are: Open Access publishing; Open and FAIR data; Open Education; and Collaboration with external partners (societal engagement, industry).</p> <p>TU/e is compliant with the Open Access publishing platform ORE. Open Science Initiatives of TU/e can be found here.</p> <p>TU/e discourages the use of metrics, such as h-index and JIF in the assessment of individual academics and requires strict compliance with the overall principles of professional scientific conduct in all cases.</p>	TU/e aims to create a database of best open science practices for academics, which will be updated periodically, to describe their activities and shape their ambitions. Although practices such as open data, code, material, publications, preregistration, clear conflict of interest, and the author CREDIT role are commonly known, they are not widely used by candidates to support their promotion documents. The inventory of best practices aims to establish examples of indicators of open science activities and how to use them as evidence in the biographical sketch.
4	Avoid the use of rankings of research organisations in research assessment	The use of rankings and especially the use of league tables is under discussion at the executive level. In individual assessment, rankings of research organizations are not used.	A national discussion between Dutch universities is taking place about the use of rankings. The proposal for concrete action is being discussed. TU/e supports the development of alternatives to league tables.
5	Commit resources, whether in the form of budget or staff capacity, to reforming research assessment as is needed to achieve the organisational changes.	In 2017, TU/e established the Interdepartmental Committees to further the quality of the academic performance and personal development evaluation and feedback at our university. Its members are senior academics. It is the ambition to increase the transparency and robustness of our evaluation methods and criteria, with specific	The HRM Squad program has committed resources and set priorities for several projects on Career and Performance, and Academic Leadership. The top priorities for Career & Performance for the upcoming years are Academic Career Paths, redesigning academic assessment procedures, developing Annual Dialogues, and developing Strategic

		<p>attention to diversity and scientific domain characteristics. The members of the Interdepartmental Committees develop mutual, in-depth insights and expertise regarding evaluating, assessing, and guiding academic talent.</p> <p>TU Eindhoven Young Academy of Engineering (EYAE) is a network of early career scientists, designers and engineers. The EYAE are a platform for young academics for open discussion; provide support for early career researchers at TU/e; foster interdisciplinary cooperation and research, excellence in education, contribute to valorization (knowledge transfer) and outreach, and advise on policies regarding scientific research, education, valorization, outreach, and impact both inside and outside TU/e.</p>	<p>Workforce Planning. These projects will be developed in co-creation with academic staff members. The Academic Leadership will further develop the leadership vision and strategy and connect the leadership programs to the TU/e values.</p>
6	<p>Review and develop research assessment criteria, tools and processes</p>	<p>The Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) is a flexible instrument that is at the service of a productive conversation on the quality and societal relevance of the research and the viability of research units in light of their own aims and strategy. The protocol leaves room for plurality with respect to the application and interpretation of the different elements, depending e.g., on the institutional context, the research discipline and the unit's nature.</p> <p>Researchers are assessed regularly by a Midterm Advisory Committee and a Promotion Assessment Committee. These committees advise the Department Boards and provide recommendations to the researchers. A first draft</p>	<p>The current SEP protocol is valid from 2021 to 2027. It is reviewed each six years by an expert group of Dutch academics. TU/e is represented in this expert group.</p> <p>In 2025, the Academic Career Paths will be further developed. A final version of the Development Matrix will be designed to ensure dynamic career paths and align with the Biographical Sketch.</p> <p>Strategic Workforce Planning will be implemented. In this plan, departments describe the talents they need in order to realise their vision and mission. Diversification is key in this respect.</p>

		of a Development Matrix was developed to diversify academic careers and put focus on quality instead of quantity.	
7	Raise awareness of research assessment reform and provide transparent communication, guidance, and training on assessment criteria and processes as well as their use	Research assessment reform is discussed regularly at the Doctorate Board (Executive Board with Deans). Furthermore, it is discussed at the meetings of the Interdepartmental Committees. New committee members participate in the course Inclusive Selection and Assessment. Assessment criteria and processes are published on the TU/e intranet pages. New developments are communicated to other stakeholders, such as the Research Support Network and the project development officers.	TU/e will create interventions for assessment committees to broaden the scope of diverse academic career paths. Increasing assessors' knowledge of diverse career paths and open science activities aims to foster an understanding of open science activities as well as an equal value of diverse career paths and the different domains. The intervention will be mandatory for core members of academic assessment.
8	Exchange practices and experiences to enable mutual learning within and beyond the Coalition	The R&R project leaders of all universities meet on a regular basis and exchange good practices. The annual R&R Festival is open to a broader community. The RRview platform has been created to share knowledge and exchange experiences within the R&R community.	Dutch universities intend to create a Dutch chapter in CoARA. This will allow all Dutch CoARA contact persons to connect, exchange good practices, and provide the national Recognition & Rewards program an international dimension.
9	Communicate progress made on adherence to the principles and implementation of the Commitments	The Action Plan will be published publicly.	Internal communication will be enhanced by creating intranet pages on CoARA and the implementation of the Commitments.
10	Evaluate practices, criteria and tools based on solid evidence and the state-of-the-art in research on research, and make data openly available for evidence gathering and research	The state-of-the-art in research on research is shared on a national level within the Recognition & Rewards network. The Business Intelligence portal provides data on the progress within TU/e and is available to all employees and students.	Evaluation of our practices, criteria and tools will take place in the HRM Squad program with a PDCA (Plan Do Check Act) cycle for continuous improvement.